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Inter-Sectoral Comparative Advantage of Tanzania and Impact on International Purchasing

By

**Bongani Muchanyuri
Macleans Mzumara**

Research Article

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^{1*}Bongani Muchanyuri and Macleans Mzumara²

^{1,2}Department of Economics, Bindura University of Science Education, P/Bag 1020, Bindura, Zimbabwe.

Email: ²macmzumara@yahoo.com

*Corresponding Author's Email: bmuchanyuri@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The authors have analyzed inter-sectoral comparative advantage of Tanzania and impact on international purchasing. Comparative advantage fairly exists in some sectors in Tanzania. Comparative disadvantage also exists mainly in the foot wear/head gear and transportation sectors. The sectors with high numbers of products have positive impact on international purchasing as they can be a competitive source to procure from. As the case may be, there is still a room in Tanzania to improve on competitiveness. It is recommended that Tanzania comes up with sectoral policies that can enhance competitiveness further. It is also recommended that a more focused export promotion strategy be promoted. Attracting foreign direct investment especially trans-national corporations can assist Tanzania to improve on its competitive advantage mainly through technology transfer.

Keywords: Comparative advantage, international trade, international purchasing, Tanzania.

INTRODUCTION

The studies which have been done on Tanzania have focused on comparative advantage in products. They have been concerned with identifying individual products in which Tanzania has comparative advantage. Therefore the recommendations have also focused on products. Although the studies generally attained their objective of identifying products in which Tanzania has comparative advantage, they fall short due to lack of identifying sectors with export capabilities hence failure to propose sectoral policies. This study fills that gap and intends to investigate inter-sectoral comparative advantage of Tanzania and the impact on international purchasing.

Tanzania is a member of the Southern African Development Community (SADC). By virtue of being a member its economic indicators have implication to the regional economy and has also implication on international purchasing. SADC has been implementing free trade in the region hence SADC member states may be motivated to source their supplies from Tanzania. By analyzing Tanzania's inter-sectoral comparative advantage could also shed light on members of SADC from which Tanzania's sector they can import from.

An analysis cannot be done without a theory to back this study. According to Goldin (1990) the theory of comparative advantage as Samuelson propagates it is the most desirable thesis in the social sciences with both the truth and without being so trivial. It is based on specialization and benefits from international trade. It is seen as a positive principle which is able to show the direction of trade as well as predicting the terms of trade. Ricardo is credited with development of the theory of comparative advantage through factor endowment in which he analyzed why Portugal was able to export wine while Britain exported cloth (Goldin, 1990). The extension of the theory of comparative advantage by the two Swedish economists Heckscher-Ohlin makes the theory more useful. They have explained how international differences in the costs of the endowments would lead countries to specialize in certain products and give up others in which they are not specialized. They propagate that a country with abundant endowments will use such endowments most intensively and produce goods which it is able to export. Then a country will import goods which use its less abundant endowments less intensively. The resultant effect of such a move is specialization. A country will specialize in the products produced by its abundant endowments and leave for other countries to specialize in the products in which it demonstrates a clear inefficiency (Mzumara, 2006). The Hecksher-Ohlin extension of the principle of comparative advantage emphasizes that the determinant of comparative advantage arise from factor endowment (Widgren, 2005). In this case international purchasing will be conducted in the same manner. Countries can source products from other countries in which they have comparative disadvantage.

According to Khatibi (2008) the relative scarcity determines comparative disadvantage. The classical theory of comparative advantage forecasts that benefits from international trade optimize welfare and that trade without restrictions brings in global prosperity (Bender and Li, 2002).

METHODOLOGY

The technique used here is Balassa (1965) revealed comparative advantage (RCA) index. The Balassa (1965) index remains the most popular and most commonly used RCA index. Generally the index is used to empirically analyze a nation's strongest industries (Serin and Civan, 2008). The Balassa method takes the form:

$$RCA = \left(\frac{X_{i,j}}{X_{w,j}} \right) / \left(\frac{X_{i,tot}}{X_{w,tot}} \right)$$

With:

$X_{i,j}$ denoting country i 's exports of product j ;

$X_{i,tot}$ denoting country i 's total exports;

$X_{w,j}$ denoting the world's (all countries) export of product j ; and

$X_{w,tot}$ denoting total exports in the world.

An RCA equal or greater than one shows that the country has a revealed comparative advantage. In other words, the exporting country of the product is relatively specialized in producing and exporting the product. An RCA of less than one shows that the country has no revealed comparative advantage and is not specialized in the product (Balassa, 1965).

The export data on Tanzania and the world export data for 2008, 2009 and 2010 were obtained from the International Trade Centre. The authors have deliberately chosen 6 digit level because it is the most disaggregate data and very much acceptable internationally.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The inter-sectoral results of Tanzania are reported in table 1.

Table 1: Inter-sectoral results of Tanzania

Rank of the sector	Sector code	Sector description	Number of products in the sector with RCA equal or greater than one
1	06-15	Vegetable products	90
2	75-50	Textiles	75
3	84-85	Machinery/electric	52
4	72-83	Metals	43
5	28-38	Chemicals and allied industries	42
6	16-24	Foodstuffs	35
7	01-05	Animal and animal products	27
8	90-97	Miscellaneous	25
9	39-40	Plastic/rubber	24
10	68-71	Stone/glass	20
11	44-49	Wood and wood products	19
11	25-27	Mineral products	19
12	41-43	Raw hides, skins, leather and furs	16
13	86-89	Transportation	5
14	64-67	Foot wear/head gear	3

Source: From the results.

Column 1 of table 1 represents ranking of the sector in terms of the number of products in which they have RCA equal or greater than one. Column 2 is the sector code being the first two digits of 6- digit product code. Column 3 is the description of the sector and column 4 is the number of products in each sector which have RCA equal or greater than one.

The results show that vegetable products sector in Tanzania ranks number one in terms of comparative advantage. The sector has 90 products with RCA equal or greater than one. In the second place is textile sector which has 75 products with RCA equal or greater than one. In the third place is machinery/electric which has 52 products. In the fourth place is metals sector with 43 products. In the fifth place is chemicals and allied industries sector with 42 products. In the sixth place is foodstuffs sector with 35 products. It is followed by animal and animal products sector with 27 products. In the eighth place is miscellaneous sector with 25 products. It is followed by plastic/rubber with 24 products. In the tenth position is stone/glass sector with 20 products. It is followed by wood and wood products and mineral products sectors with 19 products each. In the twelfth position is raw hides, skins, leather and furs. The least in comparative advantage is foot wear/head gear with 3 products only. It is seconded by transportation with 5 products. The results validate the theory of comparative advantage that a country will have some comparative advantage in some sectors and comparative disadvantage in others. In this case comparative advantage clearly exist e.g. in vegetable products and textiles sectors and comparative disadvantage in foot wear/head gear and transportation sectors.

In terms of international purchasing, other SADC member states would benefit if they source products from Tanzania's vegetable product sector. This is the most competitive sector. They will also be better off sourcing products from Tanzanian's textile sector as it has demonstrated supply capabilities. However even if removal of duty permits, other SADC members may not benefit sourcing from foot wear/head gear and transportation sectors because these sectors are less efficient. Even in the event of SADC Customs Union these sectors would lead to trade diversion. Table 2 shows top 3 products in the vegetable sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage.

Table 2: Top 3 products in the vegetable sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	080130	Cashew nuts, in shell dried	333.8222	432.4283	997.1362	587.7955
2	090700	Cloves (whole fruit, cloves and stems)	447.2478	341.3369	179.6686	322.7511
3	090190	Coffee husks and skins	219.7704	166.0342	523.089	302.9246

Source: From the results.

In table 2, cashew nuts, in shell dried in the vegetable products sector has the highest index in this sector with a value of 587.8. In the second place are cloves (whole fruit, cloves and stems) with an index value of 322.8. In the third position are coffee husks and skins with an index value of 303. Table 3 shows top 3 products in the textiles sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage.

Table 3: Top 3 products in the textiles sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	530210	True hemp fibre, raw or retted	2993.73	298.7761	0	1097.502
2	560729	Twine, cordage, ropes and cables of sisal	637.9163	2000.812	462.8954	1033.875
3	630491	Textile furnishing articles, knit or crochet	277.4687	318.9334	245.9324	267.5403

Source: From the results

In table 3, true hemp fibre, raw or retted in textiles sector has the highest RCA index in this sector with a value of 1098. In the second place is twine, cordage, ropes and cables of sisal with an index value of 1034. In the third place is textile furnishing articles, knit or crocheted with an index value of 268. Table 4 shows top 3 products in the machinery/electric sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage.

Table 4 shows top 3 products in the machinery/electric sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	850421	Liquid dielectric transformers <650KVA	151.748	3.82365	1.905871	52.49252
2	851671	Electric coffee or tea makers, domestic	47.79035	40.44095	25.74497	37.99209
3	844010	Book binding machinery including book sewing machines	85.0133	0.040666	0.723383	28.59246

Source: From the results

In table 4, liquid dielectric transformers <650KVA in the machinery/electric sector has the highest RCA index in this sector with value of 52.5. In the second place is electric coffee or tea makers, domestic with an index value of 38. In the third position is book binding machinery including book sewing machines with an index value of 28.6. Table 5 shows top 3 products in the metals sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage.

Table 5: Top 3 products in the metals sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	722860	Bar/rod, alloy steel	448.988	3.907419	5.579121	152.8249
2	761511	Pots sourers, aluminium	123.4257	96.96264	33.31236	84.56689
3	820190	Scythes, sickles etc used in agriculture etc.	131.5574	0.440878	1.324001	44.44076

Source: From the results.

In table 5, bar/rod, alloy steel in the metals sector has the highest RCA index in this sector with index value of 153. In the second place are pots sourers, aluminium with an index value of 84.6. In the third place are scythes, sickles etc used in agriculture etc, with an index value of 44. Table 6 shows top 3 products in the chemicals and allied industries sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage.

Table 6: Top 3 products in the chemicals and allied industries sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	310229	Ammonium sulphate-nitrate mix, double salts, pack >10 kg	11.42003	14.33546	335.6324	120.4626
2	320120	Wattle tanning extract	44.79998	80.30733	70.53135	65.21289
3	310559	Fertilizer with nitrogen and phosphorous <=10kg	0.015179	0	54.31864	18.11127

Source: From the results.

In table 6, Ammonium sulphate-nitrate mix, double salts, pack >10 kg in the chemical and allied industries sector has the highest RCA index in this sector with an index value of 120.5. In the second place is wattle tanning extract with an index value of 65. In the third place is fertilizer with nitrogen and phosphorous <=10kg with an index value of 18. Table 7 shows top 3 products in the foodstuffs sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage.

Table 7: Top 3 products in the foodstuffs sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	230610	Cotton seed oil-cake and other solid residues	450.9836	351.1446	289.578	363.9024
2	240120	Tobacco, unmanufactured, stemmed or stripped	116.9685	44.67404	49.27121	70.30457
3	240130	Tobacco refuse	46.01884	5.17958	139.3826	63.52701

Source: From the results.

In table 7, cotton seed oil-cake and other solid residues in the foodstuffs sector has the highest RCA index in this sector with an index value of 364. In the second place is tobacco, unmanufactured, stemmed or stripped with an index value of 70. In the third place is tobacco refuse with an index value of 64. Table 8 shows top 3 products in the animal and animal products sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage.

Table 8: Top 3 products in the animal and animal products sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	050710	Ivory, unworked or simply prepared, powder and waste	971.9802	1004.906	1294.052	1090.313
2	030261	Sardines bristling, sprats, fresh or chilled whole	118.4457	66.06162	139.3723	107.9599
3	050610	Ossein and bones treated with acid	38.83687	35.28038	153.4238	75.84703

Source: From the results.

In table 8, ivory, unworked or simply prepared, powder and waste in the animal and animal product sector has the highest RCA index in this sector with an index value of 1090. In the second rank are sardines bristling, sprats, fresh or chilled whole with an index value of 108. In the third place is ossein and bones treated with acid with an index value of 76. Table 9 shows top 3 products in the miscellaneous sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage.

Table 9: Top 3 products in the miscellaneous sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	940410	Mattress supports	41.55102	3.969449	79.74949	41.75665
2	900719	Cinematographic cameras for film >16mm wide	40.82934	30.72932	25.09368	32.21745
3	901540	Photogrammetrical surveying instruments, appliances	0	0	57.14309	19.0477

Source: From the results.

In table 9, mattress supports in the miscellaneous sector has the highest RCA in this sector with an index value of 41.8. In the second place are cinematographic cameras for film>16mm wide with an index value of 32. In the third place photogrammetrical surveying instruments, appliances with an index value of 19. Table 10 shows top 3 products in the plastic/rubber sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage.

Table 10: Top 3 products in the plastic/rubber sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	392290	Bathroom wares of plastics	26.53436	0.130693	1.491192	9.385416
2	392490	Plastic household, toilet articles not table, kitchen	4.009104	1.817857	19.31643	8.381132
3	391590	Plastic waste or scrap	1.018149	5.695606	15.46008	7.391279

Source: From the results.

In table 10, bathroom wares of plastics in plastic/rubber sector have the highest RCA in this sector with an index value of 9.4. In the second position are plastic household, toilet articles not table, kitchen with index value is 8.4. In the third place is plastic waste or scrap with an index value of 7.4. Table 11 shows top 3 products in the stone/glass sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage.

Table 11: Top 3 products in the stone/glass sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	710310	Precious, semi-precious stones unworked, partly worked	560.9394	282.655	332.249	391.9478
2	710110	Pearls natural, not permanently mounted or set	841.1959	0	0	280.3986
3	710813	Gold, semi-manufactured forms, non-monetary	40.69465	26.34062	48.25687	38.43071

Source: From the results.

In table 11, precious, semi-precious stones unworked, partly worked in the stone/glass sector has the highest RCA index in this sector with an index value of 392. In the second position are pearls natural, not permanently mounted or set with an index value of 280.4. In the third place is gold, semi-manufactured forms, non-monetary with an index value of 38. Table 12 shows top 3 products in the wood and wood products sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage.

Table 12: Top 3 products in the wood and wood products sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	440500	Wood wool, wood flour	284.2047	183.8599	172.7394	213.6013
2	440729	Lumber, tropical wood	117.2008	4.34933	1.009526	40.85322
3	440420	Poles, piles etc, non-coniferous, pointed, not sawn	45.00548	85.81624	41.28926	57.37033

Source: From the results.

In table 12, wood wool, wood flour in the wood and wood products sector has the highest RCA index in this sector with an index value of 214. In the second place is lumber, tropical wood with an index value of 40.9. In the third place are poles, piles etc, non-coniferous, pointed, not sawn with an index value of 57.4. Table 13 shows top 3 products in the mineral products sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage.

Table 13: Top 3 products in the mineral products sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	261690	Precious metal ores and concentrates except silver	1090.489	1413.098	805.1755	1102.921
2	271210	Petroleum jelly	128.4901	157.097	101.2453	128.9441
3	260200	Manganese ores, concentrates, iron ores >20% manganese	0	0	255.8885	85.29617

Source: From the results.

In table 13, precious metal ores and concentrates except silver in the mineral products sector have the highest RCA in this sector with an index value of 1103. In the second place is petroleum jelly with an index value of 129. In the third place are manganese ores, concentrates, iron ores >20% manganese with an index value of 85.3. Table 15 shows top 3 products in the raw hides, skins, leather and furs sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage.

Table 15: Top 3 products in the raw hides, skins, leather and furs sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	430190	Raw furskin pieces (e.g. heads, tails and paws)	1344.482	3066.647	2121.001	2177.377
2	430220	Tanned or dressed furskins pieces (heads, tails, paws)	1028.414	633.9097	254.6917	639.0052
3	410691	Tanned/crust hides and skins without wool/hair on in the wet state	476.3178	476.8513	281.2131	411.4608

Source: From the results.

In table 15, raw furskin pieces (e.g. heads, tails and paws) in the raw hides, skins, leather and fur sector have the highest RCA index in this sector with an index value of 2177.4. In the second place are tanned or dressed furskins pieces (heads, tails, paws) with an index value of 639. In the third place are tanned/crust hides and skins without wool/hair on in the wet state with index value of 411.5. Table 16 shows top 3 products in the transportation sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage.

Table 16: Top 3 products in the transportation sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	870520	Mobile drilling derricks	0.948033	86.62281	23.87366	37.14817
2	870110	Pedestrian controlled tractors	3.98008	0.694315	1.188183	1.954193
3	860210	Rail locomotives, diesel-electric	2.308155	1.31509	0.24319	1.28812

Source: From the results.

In table 16, mobile drilling derricks in the transportation sector has the highest RCA index in this sector with an index value of 37. In the second place are pedestrian controlled tractors with an index value of 2. In the third place are rail locomotives, diesel-electric with an index value of 1.3. Table 17 shows all 3 products in the foot wear/head gear sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage.

Table 17: All 3 products in the foot wear/head gear sector in which Tanzania has comparative advantage

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	640320	Foot wear, soles/uppers leather, strap instep and big	0.925747	5.531222	21.44331	9.300094
2	640220	Foot wear, rubber, plastic, straps fix to sole by plug	6.744508	6.161337	2.668068	5.057971
3	640192	Waterproof footwear (wellington) with no toe cap, over ankle	0.169624	0	3.008816	1.05948

Source: From the results.

In table 17, footwear, soles/uppers leather, strap instep and big in the foot wear/head gear sector have the highest RCA index in this sector with an index value of 9. In the second place are footwear, rubber, plastic, straps fix to sole by plug with an index value of 5.1. In the third place is waterproof foot wear (wellington) with no toe cap, over ankle with an index value of 1.1.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Comparative advantage fairly exists in some sectors in Tanzania. Comparative disadvantage also exists mainly in the foot wear/head gear and transportation sectors. The sectors with high numbers of products have positive impact on international purchasing as they can be a competitive source to procure from.

As the case may be, there is still a room in Tanzania to improve on competitiveness. It is recommended that Tanzania comes up with sectoral policies that can enhance competitiveness further. It is also recommended that a more focused export promotion strategy be promoted. Attracting foreign direct investment especially trans-national corporations can assist Tanzania to improve on its competitive advantage mainly through technology transfer.

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